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PROCEEDINGS

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on Sustainable organic amendment applications from a soil
and ground water management perspective
-learning, training, and knowledge exchange activity-

02-06. June 2025, Novi Sad, Serbia

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Event summary

The Summer School is organized as part of the horizon Europe TwinSubDyn project. Summer School, designed to provide a deep dive into the transformative effects of organic soil amendments on soil organic carbon, nutrient dynamics, and contaminant behavior in the soil subsurface, with profound implications for groundwater quality. This comprehensive program offers participants a unique blend of theoretical lectures and hands-on demonstrations, guided by leading experts in the field. Key Objectives: (1) Explore the intricate relationships between organic soil amendments and soil quality, focusing on carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling, and contaminant mitigation in the subsurface environment. (2) Provide attendees with practical insights and methodologies for implementing organic soil amendments to address soil and groundwater challenges effectively. (3) Foster a collaborative environment for knowledge exchange and networking among participants and experts in soil science and environmental remediation. (4) Empower early-stage researchers with essential soft skills training, including experimental design, statistical analysis, scientific writing, and navigating the landscape of ESR career development, targeting appropriate calls to participate in and how to do impactful research. During the summer school, participants will have the chance to showcase their work in their respective fields through abstract submission, and oral presentations or poster sessions.

Topics of interest

1. Long term stability of organic soil amendment,
2. Nutrient management of organic soil amendments;
3. Carbonising sewage sludge or biosolids to remove pollutants;
4. Fate and transport of emerging pollutants in organic soil amendments,

General training topics dedicated to the early-stage researchers:

5. Field experiments design and statistics;
6. Scientific writing training;
7. Round-table breakout sessions ECR career development.

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ENVIRONMENTAL FATE OF MELAMINE: BIOTRANSFORMATION IN SOIL SYSTEMS

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We are regularly exposed to a wide range of chemicals found in industrial processes, household products, and everyday environments, which can impact our health and surroundings in various ways. One such chemical is melamine, which belongs to the group of heterocyclic organic compounds and has a wide range of applications, including as a superplasticizer, in paints and coatings, and for fire-resistant foams, among others. This study investigates the biotransformation of melamine in two soils and two organic soil amendments (OSA). Experiments were conducted with two organic soil amendments: cow manure and sewage sludge, and two soils: Bayreuth soil and Danube sediment. The experimental setup includes enzyme extraction, incubation of melamine in enzyme extracts, and LC-MS/MS analysis of samples taken at selected time points during these incubations. Results indicate no biotransformation of melamine in the tested soils, which might be due to low enzyme abundance in soils, low enzyme extraction efficiency, or limited potential of enzymes to transform melamine. Incubating melamine with OSA showed its interaction with organic matter, which might be explained by the fact that melamine contains polarized amino groups (-NH₂) that can form hydrogen bonds with components of organic matter.

Keywords: Biotransformation, Organic soil amendments (OSA), Soils, Melamine

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